

CORENEXT

BRAND GUIDELINES

DECEMBER 2022

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LOGO

CONSTRUCTION

75%

CORENEXT

50%

CORENEXT

25%

CORENEXT

LOGO

VARIATIONS

HORIZONTAL

CORENEXT

ICON

VERTICAL

CORE
NEXT

VERTICAL + ICON

CORE
NEXT

LOGO

COLOR
VARIATIONS

COLOR POSITIVE

CORENEXT

BW POSITIVE

CORENEXT

COLOR NEGATIVE

CORENEXT

BW NEGATIVE

CORENEXT

PANTONE ALTERNATIVE

CORENEXT

COLOR PALETTE

MAIN PALETTE

DARK BLUE

 CMYK 100 / 100 / 26 / 24
WEB #272362
RGB 39 35 98

MEDIUM BLUE

 CMYK 88 / 77 / 0 / 0
WEB #0000FF
RGB 0 0 255

LIGHT BLUE

 CMYK 61 / 9 / 0 / 0
WEB #29BDFF
RGB 41 189 255

GRADIENT 01

GRADIENT 02

SUPPORTING PALETTE

DARK GREY

 CMYK 0 / 0 / 0 / 60
WEB #666666
RGB 102 102 102

LIGHT GREY

 CMYK 0 / 0 / 0 / 30
WEB #b3b3b3
RGB 179 179 179

PANTONE ALTERNATIVE PALETTE

 PANTONE 293C

 PANTONE 292C

TYPOG RAPHY

TITLES & HEADERS

MONTERRAT ExtraLight/Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789@&!?=(<>+ / €

[DOWNLOAD HERE](#)

MAIN TEXTS

CABIN Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789@&!?=(<>+ / €

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